

Banking Services and Financial Inclusion: A Bibliometric Journey from 2004 to 2022 Using PRISMA Guidelines

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Abstract

Banking Services and Financial Inclusion are investigated as the two keywords in the study which further provides a framework for evaluating the research directions in the field. Bibliometric analysis of 853 documents was conducted using Excel, RStudio, and the VOS viewer software. The documents were extracted and filtered from the Scopus database within the time frame of 2004–2022. To draw inferences, the Bibliometric package contains Biblioshiny, a web-based tool written in R that is employed to get main information, related sources, and authors, while VOSviewer is for making the network of keywords and countries. The first article on the subject was published in 2004 in the database. The representation of India among the top 20 sources and authors is the highest, demonstrating the importance of Financial Inclusion for a developing economy like India. The term Financial Inclusion forms a cluster with the terms Social Inclusion, Development, Financial Development, Financial Literacy, Gender, and others, indicating that the issue is significant in the development of a country by encouraging equality, social welfare, and living standards. It would facilitate the conduct of better research, which would eventually lead to more publications in the field.

Keywords: Financial Inclusion, Banking Services, Banks, Scopus, Bibliometric

Introduction

(Maity & Sahu, 2020) considered financial inclusion strategically important for society since the repercussions of financial exclusion have a significant detrimental influence on a country's economic growth since it prevents individuals from using the facilities offered by diverse financial institutions. (Garg & Agarwal, 2014) suggested that by offering financial products to those who do not have access to banking services; the government may well fulfill its aim of financial inclusion. Financial inclusion is critical in delivering economic stability to individuals and their families (Kelkar, 2014). Opening a bank account is not simply necessary for preserving and enhancing a person's social and economic position, but it is also important for satisfying all necessities (Kodan & Chhikara, 2011; Kunt & Klapper, 2013). Studies like (Aghion & Bolton, 1997; Banerjee, 2003) stated that the access to different financing activities has been a necessary element in enabling the individuals to restructure their variety of production and employment activities and to accumulate wealth. RBI and the

government contribute significantly to fostering financial inclusion for economic progress through increasing banking penetration, installing new ATMs, and implementing proactive steps around the region (Raman, 2012). (Paramasivan & Ganeshkumar, 2013) paid special emphasis on the impact of the branch concentration on financial inclusion. (Morduch, 1999) claimed that microfinance wasn't any promise but a fact, allowing over 100 million individuals to gain financial inclusion annually. Financial support, particularly for the vulnerable, oppressed and strained groups, is a requirement for employment, economic growth, poverty reduction, improved living standard, opportunities creation, business development and social cohesion since it allows people to open bank accounts, save and reinvest, safeguard their houses, and eradicate poverty (Rahman, 2009; Chakrabarty, 2011). The key to empowering poor, impoverished, and low-skilled rural families, is financial inclusion through banks (Jaiswal & Bhasin, 2015; Sarma, 2012) which leads to beneficial results in social advancement, economic progress, citizen engagement, and community empowerment (Mondal S., 2015; Mishra, 2012; Divya, 2014).

Table 1: Definition of Financial Inclusion

<i>Author</i>	<i>Definition</i>
<i>(Banerjee & Newman, 1993)</i>	“Financial inclusion refers to universal access to a wide range of financial services at a reasonable cost. These include not only banking products but also other financial services such as insurance and equity products.”
<i>(Rangarajan, 2008)</i>	“The process of ensuring access to financial services and timely and adequate credit where needed by vulnerable groups such as weaker sections and low-income groups at an affordable cost.”
<i>(Chakrabarty, 2011)</i>	“Financial inclusion is the process of ensuring access to appropriate financial products and services needed by all sections of society including vulnerable groups such as weaker sections and low-income groups at an affordable cost in a fair and transparent manner by mainstream institutional players.”

According to World Bank study published in April 2012, just 9% of individuals got new bank loans in the previous year, and only 35% of Indians had formal bank accounts, compared to 41% of emerging nations. The upgradation of financial inclusion in India is possible by encouraging rural participation (Ghosh, 2019); Demonetization (Daya & Mader, 2018); Prime Minister Jan Dhan Yojana (Dipa & Rohit, 2018); gender gap minimization (Ghosh & Vinod, 2016); increased Women participation (Beck et al., 2015); Pradhan Mantri MUDRA Yojana (Poonam & Chhikara K. S., 2022); MGNREGS (Saibal, 2017); embellishment of RRBs (Bapat et al., 2016); and financial stability of bank (Ahamed & Mallick, 2019).

Figure 1: 5 A's of Financial Inclusion

Source: Researchers' compilation using (Kaur et al., 2017)

As a result, Financial Inclusion (FI) promotes financial services and makes them available to the country's substantially poor population. It is an endeavour to support inclusive growth of the society by providing access to different financial resources available to the underserved people.

Review of related literature

The earliest pioneers associated with 'Bibliometric' analysis were (Cole & Eales, 1917), and two information analysts (Pritchard & Groos, 1969) established the basic process of bibliometrics study. (Tague et al., 1981) used bibliometric methods to identify possible research gaps in the discipline. (Ramos-Rodrguez & Ruz-Navarro, 2004; Behrens & Luksch, 2006; Liu et al., 2013) attracted attention to the use of bibliometrics' analytical and statistical tools to the disciplines of finance, commerce, and business. Numerous Free Software and Premium account application softwares, such as RStudio, Vosviewer, and many others, are accessible and are constantly being enhanced to process bibliometric records in order to derive the research trend, analyze them, and visualize them. The use of bibliometric approaches in many fields of finance and related disciplines has a long history, with several publications in the past. Bibliometric approaches have been used in several fields of finance to mine research trends, such as banking finance (Lampe & Hilgers, 2015); behavioural finance (Pimenta & Fama, 2014); development economics (Rey-Mart et al., 2016); and accounting (Merigó & Yang, 2017). Global scholars are developing information mapping in the field of finance (Huang & Ho, 2011). The researcher evaluates articles from the fields of business management, finance and economics that depict financial inclusion in the title, abstract, and keywords of the study previews.

Table 2: Previously conducted bibliometric studies on Financial Inclusion

<i>Author</i>	<i>Paper Title</i>	<i>Database</i>	<i>Documents</i>	<i>Time-frame</i>
(Gálvez-Sánchez et al., 2021)	“Research Advances on Financial Inclusion: Bibliometric Analysis”	Scopus A	1731 Articles	1986-2020
(Patel et al., 2021)	“Publication trends in Financial Inclusion: Scientometric Assessment and Visualization”	Scopus A	1550 Articles	2006-2020
(Aziz et al., 2021)	“Bibliometric Analysis of Literature on Digital Banking and Financial Inclusion Between 2014-2020”	Google Scholar, Science Direct, researchgate.com	126 Articles	2014-2020
(Chhatoi et al., 2021)	“Assessing the academic journey of financial inclusion from 2000 to 2020 through bibliometric analysis”	Scopus	463 Articles	2001-2020
(Kumar, 2022)	“Does Financial Inclusion Promote Women Empowerment with Economic Growth: A Bibliometric Approach with databases (Scopus, WOS)”	Scopus, Web of Science	300 Articles	1997-2022

Source: Authors' compilation

After a thorough investigation, the researchers observed that bibliometric analysis titled ‘Banking Services and Financial Inclusion’ had not yet been addressed. As a result of the gap, the researchers got promulgated to do a bibliometric study on the topic of 'Banking Services and Financial Inclusion'. The present research is being administered to draw the informational map and research gaps of the studies promoting 'Banking Services and Financial Inclusion'.

Objectives of the study

The primary goal of the ‘Bibliometric’ research is to assess the researchers' research status and publishing behaviour in relation to 'Banking Services and Financial Inclusion'. The following questions are addressed in the paper:

1. What is the annual production of the documents relating to ‘Banking Services and Financial Inclusion’?
2. What are the most relevant sources relating to ‘Banking Services and Financial Inclusion’?
3. What are the most relevant authors having studies related to ‘Banking Services and Financial Inclusion’?
4. What are the globally most cited documents promoting ‘Banking Services and Financial Inclusion’?
5. State the network of Keywords relating to ‘Banking Services and Financial Inclusion’.
6. State the network of Countries relating to ‘Banking Services and Financial Inclusion’.

Financial inclusion, as a growing subject, has already established its footprint in the gigantic published research to address the difficulty in choosing the sample for assessment.

Methodology

The major goal of "bibliometric analysis" is to group earlier studies regarding a specific issue (Levy & Ellis, 2006) and aid in the establishment of recommendations backed by evidences for different practitioners in the knowledge domain (Kitchenham B., 2004; Prinsen C.A., 2018; Thesenvitz et al., 2019). They are critical in assisting scholars in fully grasping a given study area (Oorschot et al., 2018). The researchers discovered three critical "bibliometric" norms: "Lotka's Law" for establishing a link between scholars and publications (Lotka,1926); "Bradford's Law" for dispersing documents on a scientific topic across scholarly journals (Bradford,1934); and "Zipf's Law" for relating the concept of relapse (Zipf,1949).

The present work is non-experimental and relies heavily on secondary data-based statistics.

Figure 2: Data filtering and visualization procedure

Source: Researchers' compilation

To uncover the net of research links between 'Financial Inclusion' and 'Banking Services,' the practical procedures of developing the "bibliometric study" were carried out. Finally, the chosen articles were scrutinized in three phases. During the first stage, on July 30, 2022, the 853 research articles of 1765 authors were retrieved from the "Scopus" database relevant to "Financial Inclusion and Banking Services."

Table 3: Data screening and filtering (Dated- July 30, 2022; Scopus)

Query	Documents
(TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Financial Inclusion") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Banking") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Banks"))	1251
(TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Financial Inclusion") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Banking") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Banks") AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA, "ECON") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA, "SOCI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA, "BUSI")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE, "ar"))	877
(TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Financial Inclusion") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Banking") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Banks") AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA, "ECON") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA, "SOCI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA, "BUSI")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE, "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE, "English"))	853

Source: Researchers' extraction using Scopus

The search results contained the "article title, names, affiliations, abstract, keywords, and references", from 2004 to 2022 which were extracted in a CSV format comprising "citation information, bibliographical information, abstract and keywords, funding details, and other documents". Excel, R 4.2.0, and VOSviewer were used to obtain the conclusions.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

The bibliometric data obtained from the Scopus database were subjected to journal, year, author, and country-specific, and keyword and country clusters analysis to investigate the academic patterns related to promoting 'Banking Services and Financial Inclusion' and gaps to be filled.

Figure 3: Main information about the study

Source: Researchers' compilation using RStudio

Table 3 presents crucial information regarding the bibliometric study, which shows that data spanning 18 years (2004–2022) was utilized to reach conclusions. The "Scopus database" yielded 853 papers with 39923 references that were deemed relevant for the study. The research incorporates the work of 1765 writers and 1923 keywords (DE).

Figure 4: Annual production of the documents related to ‘Banking Services and Financial Inclusion’ (Upto July 2022)

Source: RStudio

Figure 4 displays the annual publishing of documents linked to ‘Banking Services and Financial Inclusion’ in "Scopus" from 2004 to 2022. The first article on the subject was published in 2004, two in 2005, one in 2006; a significant increase in the number of researches on the subject, with 7, 6, 7, 5, 9, 16, 22, 23, 30, 46, 60, and 75 from 2007 to 2018; the publishing was in triple units, with 121 in 2019, 132 in 2020, 174 in 2021, and 117 in 2022 (up to July, 2022) was observed consequently in the database, demonstrating the topic's continued expansion in society and appeal among scholars worldwide.

Table 4: Most Relevant Sources related to ‘Banking Services and Financial Inclusion’

S.No.	Source/ Journal Name	Articles
1.	“INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL ECONOMICS”	22
2.	“ECONOMIC AND POLITICAL WEEKLY”	19
3.	“INDIAN JOURNAL OF FINANCE”	18
4.	“SUSTAINABILITY (SWITZERLAND)”	17
5.	“INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF APPLIED BUSINESS AND ECONOMIC RESEARCH”	16
6.	“COGENT ECONOMICS AND FINANCE”	14
7.	“BANKS AND BANK SYSTEMS”	12
8.	“APPLIED ECONOMICS”	11
9.	“ENTERPRISE DEVELOPMENT AND MICROFINANCE”	9
10.	“INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF BANK MARKETING”	9
11.	“JOURNAL OF INTERNATIONAL DEVELOPMENT”	9
12.	“JOURNAL OF MONEY LAUNDERING CONTROL”	8
13.	“INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNOLOGY RESEARCH”	7
14.	“JOURNAL OF FINANCIAL ECONOMIC POLICY”	7
15.	“QUALITATIVE RESEARCH IN FINANCIAL MARKETS”	7
16.	“TELECOMMUNICATIONS POLICY”	7
17.	“EMERGING MARKETS FINANCE AND TRADE”	6
18.	“ENVIRONMENT AND PLANNING A”	6
19.	“INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ISLAMIC AND MIDDLE EASTERN FINANCE AND MANAGEMENT”	6
20.	“LAW AND CONTEMPORARY PROBLEMS”	6

Source: Researchers’ compilation using Scopus

Figure 5: Most Relevant Sources related to ‘Banking Services and Financial Inclusion’

Source: Researchers’ compilation using RStudio

Table 5: Most Relevant Authors having research related to ‘Banking Services and Financial Inclusion’

S.No.	Author/s	Articles	Articles Fractionalized
1.	KANDPAL V	6	3.83
2.	SHERRADEN M	6	0.97
3.	ANSONG D	5	0.90
4.	CULL R	5	0.90
5.	GHOSH S	5	4.00
6.	MADALENO M	5	1.67
7.	SINGH A	5	2.67
8.	BABAJIDE AA	4	0.82
9.	BANNA H	4	1.33
10.	BARIK R	4	2.00
11.	CHOWA G	4	0.95
12.	ESOIMEME EE	4	4.00
13.	FRIEDLINE T	4	1.50
14.	MAITY S	4	2.33
15.	MUNENE JC	4	1.08
16.	SINGH K	4	2.33
17.	VO DH	4	1.33
18.	WEILL L	4	2.00
19.	AHMED F	3	0.78
20.	AJIDE FM	3	3.00

Source: Researchers’ compilation using Scopus

Figure 6: Most Relevant Authors having research related to ‘Banking Services and Financial Inclusion’

Source: Researchers’ compilation using RStudio

Table 4 and Figure 5 depict the top 20 sources (journals) that contributed to the research on ‘Banking Services and Financial Inclusion’. The top contributing journal is "International Journal of Social Economics," having 22 papers linked to Financial Inclusion and Banking Services, followed by "Economic and Political Weekly," having 19 documents. Maximum (4) of the 20 journals (i.e., "Economic and Political Weekly", "Indian Journal of Finance", "International Journal of Applied Business and Economic Research", and "International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research") were from India. Table 5 and Figure 6 shows the contributions of the top 20 authors in the domain of Financial Inclusion and Banking Services. Kandpal V. and Sherraden M. have contributed a maximum of six papers to the subject. The top 20 authors of Indian origin are Kandpal V. (six documents), Ghosh S. (six documents), Singh A. (five documents), Maity S. (four documents), Singh K. (four documents), and Ahmed F. (three documents). The analytical tables (4 and 5) along with figures (5 and 6) with a slew of journals and scholars established that ‘Banking Services and Financial Inclusion’ is an important concern in India.

Table 6: Globally Most Cited Documents promoting ‘Banking Services and Financial Inclusion’

Author/s	Year	Paper	Total Citations	Citations per Year
Sarma, M., & Pais, J.	2011	“Financial inclusion and development”	312	26.0000
Zins, A., & Weill, L.	2016	“The determinants of financial inclusion in Africa”	166	23.7143
Maurer, B.	2012	“Mobile money: Communication, consumption and change in the payments space”	140	12.7273
Fungacova, Z., & Weill, L.	2015	“Understanding financial inclusion in China”	135	16.8750
Satya, R., & Chakravarty, R. P.	2013	“Financial inclusion in India: An axiomatic approach”	106	10.6000
Schuetz, B.	2020	“Blockchain, adoption, and financial inclusion in India: Research opportunities”	105	35.0000

Ahamed, M.M., & Mallick, S.K.	2019	“Is financial inclusion good for bank stability? International evidence”	105	26.2500
Neaime, S., Gaysset, I.	2018	“Financial inclusion and stability in MENA: Evidence from poverty and inequality”	103	20.6000
Sharma, D.	2016	“Nexus between financial inclusion and economic growth: Evidence from the emerging Indian economy”	100	14.2857
Hassan, M.K., & Aliyu, S.	2018	“A contemporary survey of islamic banking literature”	97	19.4000
Allen, F., Carletti, E., Cull, R., (...), Senbet, L., Valenzuela, P.	2014	“The African financial development and financial inclusion gaps”	96	10.6667
Farah, M.F., Hasni, M.J.S., Abbas, A.K.	2018	“Mobile-banking adoption: empirical evidence from the banking sector in Pakistan”	95	19.0000
Diniz, E., Birochi, R., & Pozzebon, M.	2012	“Triggers and barriers to financial inclusion: The use of ICT-based branchless banking in an Amazon county”	91	8.2727
Abedifar, P.; Ebrahim, S.M.; Molyneux, P.; Tarazi, A.	2015	“Islamic banking and finance: Recent empirical literature and directions for future research”	88	11.0000
Mishra, V. & Singh Bisht, S.	2013	“Mobile banking in a developing economy: A customer-centric model for policy formulation”	87	4.4720
Ouma, S.A.; Odongo, T.M.; Were, M.	2017	“Mobile financial services and financial inclusion: Is it a boon for savings mobilization?”	85	6.8548
Larios-Hernández, G.J.	2017	“Blockchain entrepreneurship opportunity in the practices of the unbanked”	83	6.6935
Chauvet, L., Jacolin & L.	2017	“Financial Inclusion, Bank Concentration, and Firm Performance”	76	6.1290
Mushtaq, R. & Bruneau, C.	2019	“Microfinance, financial inclusion and ICT: Implications for poverty and inequality”	72	7.6895
Marshall, J.N.	2004	“Financial institutions in disadvantaged areas: A comparative analysis of policies encouraging financial inclusion in Britain and the United States”	71	1.0000

Source: Researchers' compilation using the Scopus database

Table 6 contains the details of the most cited 20 documents globally related to 'Banking Services and Financial Inclusion' by different authors in the 'Scopus' database up to July, 2022. (Sarma M. & Paris J.) topped the list with a total of 312 citations - 26 citations per year on the document titled "Financial inclusion and development" published in the year 2011 followed by (Zins, A., & Weill, L.) having a total of 166 citations with 23.7143 citations per year on the document titled "The determinants of financial inclusion in Africa" published in 2016. Only two documents titled "Blockchain, adoption, and financial inclusion in India: Research opportunities" and "Is financial inclusion good for bank stability? International evidence" of the authors (Schuetz, B. (2020); Ahamed, M.M., & Mallick, S.K. (2019)) also got the equal number of citations (i.e., 105). Among 20, 5 most globally cited documents belong to India.

Figure 7: 'Banking Services and Financial Inclusion' Keyword Cluster

Source: Researchers' compilation using VOSviewer

Figure 7 illustrates a cluster of keywords based on papers linked to 'Banking Services and Financial Inclusion'. Type of Analysis: Co-occurrence; Unit of Analysis: All Keywords; Counting method: Full Counting; A minimum of ten keywords are utilized. Out of 2449 keywords, 64 match the above-mentioned criteria, and 7 Clusters are generated, which are: Cluster 1: 15 items (Accessibility, Banking, Developing World, Economic Development, Economic Growth, Employment, Financial Crisis, Financial Exclusion, Financial Market, Financial Policy, Financial System, Institutional Framework, Sub-Saharan Africa, Sustainability, Sustainable Development); Cluster 2: 11 items (Bangladesh, Development, Financial Development, Financial Inclusion, Financial Institutions, Financial Literacy, Gender, Islamic Banking, Islamic Finance, Pakistan, Social Inclusion); Cluster 3: 10 items (Credit, Credit Provision, India, Microfinance, Poverty, Poverty Alleviation, Rural Area, Rural Finance, Savings, World Bank); Cluster 4: 9 items (Banking Services, Banks, Education, Financial Services, Mobile Banking, Nigeria, South Africa, Technology, Technology adoption); Cluster 5: 8 items (Bank Account, Developing Countries, Electronic Money, Finance, Financial Inclusions, Human, Mobile Money, Unbanked); Cluster 6: 6 items (Blockchain, China, Financial Regulation, Financial Stability, Fintech, Lending behaviour); and Cluster 7: 5 items (Africa, Financial Inclusion Index, Innovation, Panel Data, Regression Analysis). Cluster 5 shows the link between the keywords Bank Account, Financial Inclusions, Unbanked, and developing countries which shows that banking services play a key role in promoting Financial Inclusion in developing countries.

Figure 8.1: Cluster of Countries pertaining to ‘Banking Services and Financial Inclusion’

Source: Researchers’ compilation using VOSviewer

Figure 8.2: Country Collaboration Map

Country Collaboration Map

Figure 8.1 and 8.2 displays the cluster of nations created based on the information utilized for analysis (Type: Co-authorship; Unit: Countries; Minimum no. of documents of a country: 5; Normalization method: Association Strength) from the data extracted from the database. 46 countries out of 112 meet the criteria, and 9 Clusters are formed, which are: Cluster 1: 10 items (Cote d'Ivoire, Germany, Italy, Japan, Mexico, Netherlands, Spain, Taiwan, Uganda, Vietnam); Cluster 2: 7 items (Belgium, Cameroon, China, Hungary, Nigeria, Pakistan, Palestine); Cluster 3: 7 items (Bangladesh, Finland, India, Indonesia, Malaysia, Switzerland, United Kingdom); Cluster 4: 6 items (Egypt, Jordan, Portugal, Saudi Arabia, Turkey, United Arab Emirates); Cluster 5: 6 items (Colombia, Ghana, Hongkong, Kenya, South Korea, United States); Cluster 6: 3 items (Australia, Brazil, Canada); Cluster 7: 3 items (France, Poland, Russian Federation); Cluster 8: 3 items (New Zealand, South Africa, Zimbabwe); and Cluster 9: 1 item (Singapore).

Conclusion

In the backdrop of the advancement in banking services, this study aims to elucidate the phenomenon of financial inclusion. The current study examined documents from the "Scopus" database relating to 'Banking Services and Financial Inclusion' to determine the topic's relevance from 2004 to 2022. The research assesses the development of financial inclusion through banking services, with a focus on "Business Management, Social Science, and Economics." Bibliometric analyses identify noteworthy publications and then carefully describe as to how they connect to some research issue, including other papers referenced. There was a positive publishing trend during the research period, and it gave helpful information to scholars looking for reviews with possibly high citations. The study aims to address the most relevant authors and publications, as well as a cluster of nations working and keywords on the topic 'Banking Services and Financial Inclusion'. In 2004, the first paper on the subject was published. The term 'Financial Inclusion' forms a cluster with the terms Social Inclusion, Development, Financial Development, Financial Literacy, Gender, and others, indicating that the issue is significant in the development of a country through encouraging equality, social welfare, living standards, and so on. The representation of India among the top 20 sources and authors demonstrates the importance of Financial Inclusion for a developing economy like India by mostly partnering with nations such as Bangladesh, the United Kingdom, Indonesia, Malaysia, Finland, and Switzerland, all of which are actively engaged in the same sector establishing further that India is very significant among the nations documented on financial inclusion. As Financial inclusion is characterized by the availability and equitability of opportunities to access financial products and describes a procedure through which individuals and companies may obtain appropriate, inexpensive, and timely financial goods and services (Chhatoi et al., 2021), emphasizing the topic's importance for India by providing rich results and essential information for further studies after vividly examining the concept since its inception from many perspectives benefitting the researchers, policymakers, and intellectuals.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

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